

Comparative Study of Technology Acceptance Models for Academic Information Systems: A Theoretical Review

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 01 October 2025	This study presents a comparative theoretical review of four major models is Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS), and the DeLone & McLean IS Success Model in the context of Academic Information Systems (AIS). Drawing from literature published between 2000 and 2025, with emphasis on recent studies (2021–2025), the paper highlights the strengths and limitations of each framework. The findings indicate that TAM is simple and effective for explaining early adoption, UTAUT provides a more comprehensive analysis by including organizational and social factors, EUCS is suitable for assessing student satisfaction, and the DeLone & McLean model offers a holistic view of AIS success. The main contribution of this paper is to provide theoretical guidance for both researchers and practitioners in selecting appropriate models for AIS evaluation. As a conceptual review, this study does not include empirical testing; therefore, future research should validate these insights using methods such as PLS-SEM or SmartPLS and consider hybrid approaches that integrate multiple models.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Academic Information Systems (AIS) play a crucial role in modern universities by enhancing the efficiency of administrative tasks, supporting research activities, and facilitating the learning process [1]. Studies from 2021 to 2024 show that AIS significantly improve administrative efficiency by reducing manual errors, accelerating access to academic data, and increasing inter-departmental coordination, thus supporting good university governance and management [2]. Moreover, AIS supports effective online learning, particularly during the COVID-19 pandemic, by enabling flexible and accessible learning environments through web and mobile platforms [3]. The integration of artificial intelligence and digital collaboration tools within AIS is also advancing personalized learning and collaborative educational approaches, enhancing student engagement and academic performance [4]. These developments show the strategic importance of AIS not only in operational management but also as enablers of innovation in teaching and research in higher education institutions.

The success of adopting Academic Information Systems (AIS) varies across institutions primarily due to differences in user acceptance and satisfaction. Research indicates that system quality, information quality, and service quality influence user satisfaction, which in turn affects the overall success of AIS implementation in universities [5]. Although numerous acceptance and success models such as the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), and DeLone dan McLean Success Model have been used to evaluate these factors, there is a notable lack of systematic comparative studies assessing their effectiveness in different academic contexts [6]; [7]; [8]. This gap restricts understanding of which model is most appropriate for specific university environments, underscoring the need for comprehensive comparative research to guide institutions in selecting the optimal evaluation frameworks and strategies to improve AIS acceptance and success.

The main objective of this study is to compare four widely recognized models in the field of technology acceptance and information system success, namely the

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), the End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) model, and the DeLone and McLean Information System Success Model. This comparison is situated within the context of Academic Information Systems (AIS) in order to highlight the strengths and limitations of each framework in explaining user acceptance, satisfaction, and overall system success. By conducting a comprehensive conceptual review, this study aims not only to clarify the theoretical distinctions among these models but also to demonstrate their relevance to the implementation of AIS in higher education institutions.

The significance of this research lies in its potential to provide theoretical guidance for both scholars and practitioners. For researchers, the findings serve as a reference point in selecting or adapting an appropriate theoretical model for empirical investigations in the AIS domain. For practitioners, particularly system administrators and decision-makers in universities, this review offers valuable insights into which model is most suitable for evaluating user adoption, satisfaction, and long-term effectiveness of AIS.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), originally proposed by Davis (1989), remains one of the most influential frameworks to explain the adoption of technology [9]. TAM posits that two central constructs Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU), which significantly predict users' intention to adopt new systems [10]. The proposed model was subsequently revised, the final framework proposed by Venkatesh and Davis (1996) indicated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. TAM by Venkatesh and Davis (1996)

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) consists of five core constructs. The first is Perceived Usefulness, which refers to an individual’s belief that using a particular information system can support decision-making processes. When users consider a system beneficial, their likelihood of adopting it increases. The second is Perceived Ease of Use, which reflects the extent to which an individual believes that the technology is simple to operate. A system perceived as easy to use will encourage greater acceptance. The third construct is the Attitude toward Using Technology, describing a person’s positive or negative feelings about

utilizing the system. The fourth is Behavioral Intention to Use, which is shaped by both perceived usefulness and attitude toward technology. Finally, the fifth construct is Actual Use, representing the real practice of employing the system. The perception that a system is easy to use is also linked to the individual’s confidence in their own ability to operate it effectively [11].

In academic settings, TAM has been widely applied to understand how students, faculty, and staff decide to utilize or reject Academic Information Systems (AIS), as these perceptions strongly influence their acceptance and sustained usage of institutional digital platforms [12]. Recent studies have reinforced TAM’s predictive power and have further extended it by integrating relevant antecedents such as management support and training that affect PU and PEOU in AIS contexts [13].

One of the strengths of TAM lies in its simplicity and ease of application. Researchers frequently adopt it as a parsimonious framework that requires only a few variables while still offering strong explanatory power in predicting system acceptance [14]. Its minimalism makes it highly adaptable to diverse contexts, including higher education institutions that deploy learning management systems or registration platforms. However, TAM has also been criticized for its limited consideration of social and organizational factors. For example, it often neglects external influences such as peer pressure, institutional support, or cultural dimensions, which are particularly important in collaborative academic settings [15].

In recent years, TAM has been widely applied in empirical studies of AIS. For instance, Dai et al. conducted a longitudinal study on Chinese students’ use of LMS platforms during the shift to online learning, finding that both PU and PEOU significantly improved over time as users became more experienced [16]. In Indonesia, Sukandi et al. examined the adoption of Telkom University’s LMS by combining TAM and other frameworks, reporting that PU and PEOU strongly influenced students’ behavioral intentions [17]. In Malaysia, Annamalai et al. investigated Learning Management System (LMS) use for distance education through an extended TAM, finding that perceived ease of use and perceived resources significantly determine attitude and actual use of LMS among working adults [18].

Similarly, Chuenyindee et al. integrated TAM with task, technology fit, and usability measures to assess LMS adoption during the COVID-19 pandemic and confirmed that PU is the most consistent predictor of user satisfaction [14]. Also, in Indonesia, Padalia et al. studied e-learning application usage in higher education (Universitas Negeri Makassar) using TAM to explore how students’ perceptions of usefulness and ease of use affect their intention and actual usage. The findings indicated significant relationships between perceived usefulness and attitude, as well as between attitude and behavioral intention [19].

Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT)

The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), introduced by Venkatesh et al. 2003, consolidates key constructs from earlier technology-acceptance models to explain users’ behavioral intention and subsequent usage behaviour [20]. The core direct determinants in UTAUT as shown in Figure 2 are Performance Expectancy (the degree to which using a technology will provide benefits in job performance), Effort Expectancy (ease of use), Social Influence (perceived social pressure to use), and Facilitating Conditions (availability of resources and support). The original model also proposes moderators such as gender, age, experience, and voluntariness of use, which allow researchers to test how the strength of these relationships varies across user groups [21].

Figure 2. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (2003)

UTAUT’s strengths for academic information systems are its predictive power and relative parsimony, it often explains a large proportion of variance in behavioral intention and use when applied to learning technologies [20]. Because UTAUT explicitly models both perceived usefulness (performance expectancy) and perceived ease (effort expectancy), it is well suited to study student and faculty acceptance of systems such as LMS, student information systems, or AI-based educational tools [22]. However, this model presents practical challenges, such as the expansion and customization into UTAUT2. The model also has notable limitations because its structure is relatively complex and requires the inclusion of multiple variables, which makes it more demanding in terms of data requirements and sample size. This complexity can be a barrier for researchers who work with smaller populations or limited resources[21].

Recent empirical applications illustrate UTAUT’s continued relevance in higher education. A large PLS-SEM study of students’ continuance intention toward e-learning platforms found that performance expectancy, hedonic/learning value, habit, and e-satisfaction significantly influenced continued usage [23]. Research on mobile learning acceptance during the COVID-19 era used UTAUT2 adaptations to cluster user profiles and showed that demographic moderators (age, experience) shaped which constructs most strongly predicted use [22].

UTAUT has been widely applied to mobile learning and online registration systems in universities, with many studies finding that performance expectancy and facilitating conditions are significant predictors of actual system use among students. This makes UTAUT useful for AIS contexts where institutional infrastructure and perceived benefits matter [24]. More recently, studies applying UTAUT2 to AI tools in higher education (e.g., ChatGPT) demonstrate that extending the model (adding habit, hedonic motivation, or personal innovativeness) helps capture adoption dynamics for novel technologies [25].

End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS)

End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) is a widely adopted framework to measure user satisfaction with information systems, emphasizing the experience after system use rather than before adoption [26]. According to the results of research conducted by Doll and Torkzadeh as shown in Figure 3, the model assesses satisfaction through five dimensions is content, accuracy, format, timeliness, and ease of use, which together provide a comprehensive evaluation of how well a system supports users in performing their tasks [27]. Recent studies in higher education contexts show that these dimensions are highly relevant for evaluating academic information systems, as they directly reflect whether students and faculty perceive the system as useful, reliable, and easy to navigate [28].

Figure 3. Research EUCS Model by Doll & Torkzadeh

Despite its strengths, EUCS presents a key limitation, as it focuses primarily on post-use satisfaction and does not capture intention-to-use, which is crucial when analyzing system adoption behavior [29]. For this reason, EUCS is often integrated with technology acceptance models, such as TAM or UTAUT, to provide a more holistic analysis that includes both adoption intentions and user satisfaction outcomes [30]. This combination allows researchers to capture not only how effective a system is after being used, but also the factors influencing whether users are willing to adopt it in the first place.

Hidayah et al. present a study that applies the End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) method to measure user satisfaction with academic information systems. The research identifies key dimensions such as system quality, information quality, and service quality that significantly impact users' satisfaction levels. The results offer practical

implications for improving academic information systems to better meet the needs and expectations of their users in educational institutions [31].

The study by Padalia et al. investigates the application of the End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) model to evaluate student satisfaction with Learning Management Systems (LMS) in universities. By analyzing key factors influencing user satisfaction, the research highlights the critical role of system quality, information quality, and service quality in shaping students' overall satisfaction with LMS platforms. The findings provide valuable insights for higher education institutions aiming to enhance LMS effectiveness and improve the learning experience [32].

Another case is from Saputri et al. examine the impact of academic information systems on student satisfaction in higher education. Their study highlights how system usability, accessibility, and reliability contribute significantly to enhancing students' overall satisfaction with academic services. The findings underscore the importance of optimizing information systems to support effective learning and administrative processes within universities. Their quantitative analysis showed that speed, timeliness, and ease of access (dimensions relevant to EUCS) significantly contributed to overall satisfaction [33].

DeLone & McLean IS Success Model

The DeLone & McLean Information Systems (IS) Success Model, first introduced in 1992 and revised in 2003, remains a fundamental framework for evaluating the effectiveness of information systems, particularly in an academic context [34]. The 2003 update notably introduced Service Quality as a distinct dimension, highlighting the importance of user support and service for IS success [35]. The model theorizes causal relationships among these dimensions, whereby the quality variables influence Use and User Satisfaction [36].

According to DeLone and McLean as shown in Figure 4, the model has six dimensions System Quality, Information Quality, Service Quality, Use, User Satisfaction, and Net Benefits [37]. Its major strength is its comprehensiveness: it captures both technical aspects (system, information, service) and human/outcome aspects (use, satisfaction, net benefits). This makes it a good fit for long-term evaluation of academic information systems where multiple stakeholders (students, faculty, and administration) have different needs [38].

Figure 4. D&M is an updated success model (2003)

Despite its broad applicability, the D&M model poses several challenges. First, the measurement demands are high, requiring several interdependent constructs to be defined, measured, and validated. Often using advanced statistical techniques such as PLS-SEM or SEM. In academic settings with limited respondents, such as specialized departments or small cohorts, this complexity may reduce the model's practicality. [39]. Second, in some studies, not all hypothesized paths are supported. For example, in a validation study of the Student Information System (SIM) in Turkey, Use, System Quality, Information Quality, and Service Quality significantly affected Use, but some other dimensions (such as specific paths to User Satisfaction or Net Benefit) were not significant [38]. Third, the complexity of the model can make data collection, model fitting, and interpretation more time-consuming, especially in settings with limited resources or where the number of respondents is restricted [39].

Empirical applications in the last few years show D&M's strong relevance for academic systems. For example, The DeLone and McLean model for measuring success in online learning systems: Indonesian evidence. Applied the model to Online Learning Systems (OLS) and found that platform quality (analogous to System Quality) had a positive influence on OLS success mediated by Use and User Satisfaction [39]. Similarly, The Delone and McLean Information System Success Model: Investigating User Satisfaction in Learning Management System. Found that Information Quality, System Quality, and Service Quality significantly predicted User Satisfaction in an LMS context [40]. Sukandi et al. in their Telkom University LMS study employed DeLone & McLean dimensions to assess system success, finding that system, information, and service quality significantly affect student perceptions of AIS success when combined with acceptance variables [41]. These studies illustrate that D&M not only provides explanatory power but also offers practical diagnostic feedback for which quality dimensions require prioritization in academic information systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study adopts a theoretical review and conceptual analysis approach to compare four prominent technology

acceptance and information system success models (TAM, UTAUT, EUCS, and DeLone & McLean) in the context of Academic Information Systems (AIS). Theoretical reviews are appropriate when the objective is to clarify conceptual distinctions, synthesize theoretical developments, and articulate implications for future empirical research and practice [42]

Data Sources and Search Strategy

The literature search targeted major academic databases and indexes, namely Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, complemented by forward/backward citation chasing of key articles. The temporal scope covers publications from 2000 to 2025, with particular attention to studies published between 2021 and 2025, because recent empirical work offers the most relevant evidence on AIS adoption and success during the large-scale shift to online learning. Search keywords included combinations of terms such as: "Technology Acceptance Model", "TAM", "UTAUT", "End-User Computing Satisfaction", "EUCS", "DeLone and McLean", "information system success", "learning management system", "academic information system", and "higher education". The search strategy followed best practices for transparent literature identification and reporting [43].

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion criteria for this review focused on peer-reviewed journal articles, book chapters, and reputable conference papers that examined TAM, UTAUT, EUCS, or the DeLone & McLean model in the context of Academic Information Systems (AIS) or Learning Management Systems (LMS). Both empirical studies, conceptual discussions, and review papers published between 2000 and 2025 were considered, with particular attention given to more recent work from 2021 to 2025. Publications in both Indonesian and English were included to capture perspectives from national and international contexts. Studies were excluded if they were conducted outside the higher education sector without transferable insights or if they lacked sufficient methodological detail to support meaningful comparison.

Screening and Data Extraction

Initial searches yielded a broad set of candidate records. After deduplication, titles and abstracts were screened for relevance, and full texts were assessed against inclusion criteria. For each included article, the following information was extracted into a structured matrix: author and year, country or context, AIS type, model applied, variables, main findings, and noted strengths or limitations [44].

Analytical Approach

The core analytic task of this study was to conduct a conceptual comparison of the four models across several dimensions, including the primary variables measured, their

theoretical focus, their respective strengths and limitations, and their relevance for evaluating Academic Information Systems (AIS). To achieve this, a matrix-based synthesis was employed to organize constructs and empirical evidence according to these dimensions. The results of this process were then integrated into a narrative discussion that highlights both the points of convergence and divergence among the models, as well as their broader implications [45].

Trustworthiness and Limitations

To enhance trustworthiness, peer-reviewed sources were prioritized, search strings documented, and findings triangulated across national and international studies. Nevertheless, as a theoretical review the study does not estimate pooled effect sizes and is subject to interpretive bias inherent in narrative synthesis. This study therefore present findings as conceptual judgments and propose empirical tests as future work to validate model comparisons in specific AIS settings. The methodological choices reflect established guidance for integrative and narrative reviews while acknowledging their scope and limits [46].

IV. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Comparative Framework of Models

The comparative table presented below is developed by the authors based on a synthesis of key theoretical sources (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh et al., 2003; Doll & Torkzadeh, 1988; DeLone & McLean, 2003) and recent applications of these models in the context of academic information systems. The table does not replicate any single study, but instead integrates theoretical constructs, empirical findings, and practical insights to provide a structured comparison across models. This synthesis is intended to guide both researchers and practitioners in selecting the most appropriate framework according to their objectives and contexts.

Table 1. Comparative Table of Models

Model	Key Variables	Focus	Strengths	Limitations	Relevance to AIS
TAM [9]	PU, PEOU, Attitude, Intention, Use	User acceptance	Simple, parsimonious, strong predictive power [16]; [14]	Ignores social & organizational context	Useful for initial adoption studies of LMS & AIS
UTAUT [20]	Performance expectancy, Effort expectancy	Acceptance & use	Broad explanatory power, accounts for moderato	Complex, demanding	Strong fit for institutional adoption &

	ncy, Social influence, Facilitating conditions		rs (age, gender, etc.) [22]; [15]	No adoption dimension, limited to satisfaction [32]; [33]	Good for evaluating AIS service quality & student satisfaction
EUCS [27]	Content, Accuracy, Format, Timeliness, Ease of use	Post-use satisfaction	Focuses on user experience, practical for assessing satisfaction [32]; [33]	No adoption dimension, limited to satisfaction [32]; [33]	Good for evaluating AIS service quality & student satisfaction
DeLone & McLean [37]	System quality, Information quality, Service quality, Use, User satisfaction, Net benefits	IS Success	Comprehensive, multidimensional [38]; [39]	Complex model, requires large sample & SEM	Best for long-term AIS success evaluation

As such, the table should be viewed as a conceptual framework generated from the literature review rather than a reproduction of an existing study. It reflects interpretation of the strengths, limitations, and relevance of each model for evaluating Academic Information Systems in higher education.

Narrative Analysis

The TAM has consistently demonstrated its value in explaining the early stages of AIS adoption. Its focus on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use provides a parsimonious yet powerful framework to predict user attitudes and behavioral intentions [16]. Studies in higher education confirm that TAM remains effective in contexts where institutions are introducing or upgrading learning management systems, particularly in explaining why students and faculty decide to initially engage with a new system [14]. However, its strength in simplicity also reflects its main limitation: the model does not fully capture social and institutional dynamics that increasingly shape AIS adoption.

UTAUT extends the predictive scope by integrating constructs such as performance expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, making it especially relevant for

large organizational settings [22]. For AIS in universities, this model is advantageous because it accounts for institutional support, peer influence, and demographic moderators like age or prior experience. Empirical studies in higher education suggest that UTAUT offers richer insights than TAM when evaluating adoption across diverse user groups and campuses with complex technological infrastructures [15]. Nevertheless, its comprehensiveness requires more complex data collection and statistical techniques, which may pose challenges in smaller-scale AIS studies.

Unlike TAM and UTAUT, EUCS does not focus on adoption or intention, but instead emphasizes the user’s post-adoption experience. EUCS dimensions is content, accuracy, timeliness, ease of use, and format, make it highly relevant for assessing the quality of AIS from the perspective of end users [32]. Research in Indonesian universities has shown that EUCS is a reliable tool to evaluate whether AIS deliver accurate and timely information that meets student and faculty needs [33]. The model’s limitation lies in its narrow scope: while it measures satisfaction effectively, it does not explain why users adopt or reject AIS in the first place.

The DeLone and McLean model provides the broadest evaluative lens by combining system, information, and service quality with user satisfaction, usage, and net benefits. This multidimensional approach enables a holistic assessment of AIS performance, from technical quality to institutional impact [38]. Recent studies highlight that this model is particularly effective in identifying how AIS contribute to long-term educational outcomes and organizational efficiency[39]. While comprehensive, its application can be resource-intensive, requiring larger samples and advanced analysis to capture the interrelationships among constructs.

Overall, TAM and UTAUT primarily focus on user acceptance, with TAM offering simplicity and UTAUT providing greater contextual depth. In contrast, EUCS is limited to measuring satisfaction, while the DeLone & McLean model offers a multidimensional evaluation. This direct comparison underscores that model selection should be aligned with research objectives and stakeholder needs rather than assuming one framework fits all contexts.

V. DISCUSSION

The comparative analysis of TAM, UTAUT, EUCS, and the DeLone & McLean IS Success Model highlights that each framework offers unique contributions to the evaluation of Academic Information Systems (AIS). Importantly, the relevance of each model depends on the stakeholder perspective and the stage of system use.

For students, the EUCS model appears most suitable because its focus on accuracy, timeliness, ease of use, format, and content directly reflects the everyday user experience [32]. As students are the primary end-users of AIS, particularly in contexts such as learning management

systems or online registration. Measuring satisfaction through EUCS provides actionable feedback on usability and information quality [33]. For faculty and administrative staff, adoption and continued use are more critical. In these contexts, TAM and UTAUT offer stronger explanatory power by focusing on constructs such as perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, performance expectancy, and facilitating conditions [16]. These models are particularly helpful for understanding how individual and organizational factors influence willingness to adopt new AIS features and integrate them into teaching or administrative workflows [22].

From a managerial perspective, universities require a broader assessment of AIS that extends beyond individual acceptance or satisfaction. The DeLone & McLean model provides such a holistic evaluation by incorporating system, information, and service quality as well as user satisfaction, usage, and net benefits [38]. This makes it valuable for decision-makers who need to justify investments, measure institutional outcomes, and ensure the long-term success of AIS implementations [39].

Overall, these insights suggest that no single model is universally sufficient for evaluating AIS. Instead, researchers and practitioners should consider adopting a combined approach that leverages the strengths of multiple models. For example, using TAM or UTAUT to explain initial adoption, EUCS to monitor ongoing satisfaction, and DeLone & McLean to assess overall success and institutional impact. Such integration not only aligns evaluation with different stakeholders but also provides a more comprehensive understanding of how AIS contribute to academic effectiveness and organizational sustainability.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study compared four important models in the context of Academic Information Systems (AIS): the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS), and the DeLone & McLean IS Success Model. The analysis highlighted that each framework has distinct strengths and limitations depending on the purpose of evaluation and the stakeholder perspective.

Overall, TAM provides a simple yet powerful tool to explain initial adoption of AIS, while UTAUT offers a more comprehensive view by integrating social and organizational influences, though at the cost of complexity. EUCS focuses specifically on post-adoption satisfaction, making it particularly relevant for evaluating the student experience. Meanwhile, the DeLone & McLean model offers the most holistic assessment by addressing system quality, information quality, service quality, user satisfaction, use, and net benefits.

The key contribution of this paper lies in offering a comparative perspective that can guide both researchers and

practitioners in selecting the most appropriate theoretical model to assess AIS adoption, satisfaction, and success. However, as a conceptual review, the study is limited by the absence of empirical validation. Future research should therefore test these comparative insights empirically, for instance by applying structural equation modeling (e.g., SmartPLS) to integrated frameworks that combine the strengths of multiple models.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding this research.

REFERENCES

1. I. Putriyani, B. Bayu Sugiharto, and F. Ramadhan, “Analisis Literatur Tentang Peran Sistem Informasi Akademik Dalam Meningkatkan Efisiensi Administrasi Di Institusi Perguruan Tinggi,” *J-CEKI: Jurnal Cendekia Ilmiah*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 2283–2289, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.56799/JCEKI.V4I1.5881.
2. R. A. Sunarjo, M. H. R. Chakim, S. Maulana, and G. Fitriani, “Management of Educational Institutions through Information Systems for Enhanced Efficiency and Decision-Making,” *International Transactions on Education Technology (ITEE)*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 47–61, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.33050/itee.v3i1.670.
3. I. Maskanah, U. Kristen Satya Wacana Herlin Lusiana Sae, and U. Kristen Satya Wacana, “Efektivitas Penggunaan Teknologi Dalam Pembelajaran Daring Di Masa Pandemi Covid-19,” *JURNAL JENDELA PENDIDIKAN*, vol. 1, no. 04, pp. 279–285, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.57008/JJP.V1I04.60.
4. R. Aprianto, E. P. Lestari, Sadan, and E. Fletcher, “Harnessing Artificial Intelligence in Higher Education: Balancing Innovation and Ethical Challenges,” *International Transactions on Education Technology (ITEE)*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 84–93, Nov. 2024, doi: 10.33050/ITEE.V3I1.680.
5. K. Dwi, S. I*1, T. Chamidy, and M. Faisal, “Analysis of Academic Information System Using Information System Success Model and System Quality Model Case Study of Institut Teknologi Nasional Malang,” *Transactions on Informatics and Data Science*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 33–44, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.24090/TIDS.V1I1.12234.
6. A. Permadi, T. Irawati, and B. Widada, “Analisis Perilaku Pengguna Website Sistem Informasi Akademik Menggunakan Technology Acceptance Model (TAM),” *Jurnal Teknologi Informasi dan Komunikasi (TIKomSiN)*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 17–24, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.30646/tikomsin.v11i1.728.

7. S. A. Melgis, R. Aryani, D. Lestari, and M. N. A. Abdunazar, “Analyzing the Quality of Academic Information Systems on System Success,” *INTENSIF: Jurnal Ilmiah Penelitian dan Penerapan Teknologi Sistem Informasi*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 144–165, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.29407/INTENSIF.V8I1.21512.
8. S. Yusuf, M. I. Abas, S. Syahrial, and R. Lamusu, “Penerapan Model Unified Theory Of Acceptance And Use Of Technology (Utaut) Terhadap Penggunaan Sistem Informasi Akademik Universitas Muhammadiyah Gorontalo,” *Jurnal Ilmu Komputer (JUIC)*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 31–36, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.31314/JUIC.V2I2.1714.
9. F. D. Davis, “Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology,” *MIS Q*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 319–339, 1989, doi: 10.2307/249008.
10. O. Tikaromah, A. Yahya, T. Hidayat, and F. Ekonomi dan Bisnis, “Technology Acceptance Model dalam Mendorong Intention to use pada Sistem Informasi Akuntansi,” *Jurnal Akuntansi Bisnis Pelita Bangsa*, vol. 9, no. 02, pp. 246–256, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.37366/AKUBIS.V9I02.2278.
11. M. Y. Rukmana, F. A. Bactiar, and S. R. Akbar, “Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) on distance learning in University of Brawijaya,” *Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 331–348, Jan. 2025, doi: 10.25126/JITECS.93724.
12. A. Azimah and R. Ria, “The Role of Technology Acceptance Model for Exploring Application of Accounting Information System Based on Artificial Intelligence,” *Kurdish Studies*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 5571–5581, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.58262/ks.v12i2.413.
13. A. Budiyanto, “Penerapan Metode Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Terhadap Penggunaan Aplikasi Sistem Informasi Akademik Institut Bisnis Nusantara,” *Jurnal Esensi Infokom : Jurnal Esensi Sistem Informasi dan Sistem Komputer*, vol. 7, no. 2, pp. 98–102, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.55886/INFOKOM.V7I2.776.
14. T. Chuenyindee *et al.*, “The perceived usability of the learning management system during the COVID-19 pandemic: Integrating system usability scale, technology acceptance model, and task-technology fit,” *Work*, vol. 73, no. 1, pp. 41–58, Jul. 2022, doi: 10.3233/WOR-220015.
15. L. Xue, A. M. Rashid, and S. Ouyang, “The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) in Higher Education: A Systematic Review,” *Sage Open*, vol. 14, no. 1, Jan. 2024, doi: 10.1177/21582440241229570.
16. Y. Dai, X. Lin, and L. Li, “Technology Acceptance of LMS—Do Previous Online Learning Experiences Matter?,” *Journal of Educational Technology Development and Exchange (JETDE)*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 75–90, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.18785/jetde.1402.04.
17. V. S. Sukandi and M. Ariyanti, “Analysis acceptance and use of CeLOE learning management system (LMS) Telkom University using unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) and Delone-McLean Model,” *Contemporary Research on Management and Business*, pp. 252–255, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1201/9781003295952-64.
18. N. Annamalai, T. Ramayah, J. A. Kumar, and S. Osman, “Investigating the Use of Learning Management System (LMS) for Distance Education in Malaysia: A Mixed-Method Approach,” *Contemp Educ Technol*, vol. 13, no. 3, p. ep313, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.30935/CEDETECH/10987.
19. A. Padalia, Jamilah, Syakhruni, Y. S. Rini, and A. M. Idkhan, “E-Learning Application Usage in Higher Education with Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) for Students’ Assessment,” *Int J Adv Sci Eng Inf Technol*, vol. 13, no. 3, pp. 1059–1067, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.18517/IJASEIT.13.3.18691.
20. V. Venkatesh, M. G. Morris, G. B. Davis, and F. D. Davis, “User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view,” *MIS Q*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 425–478, 2003, doi: 10.2307/30036540.
21. K. Tamilmani, N. P. Rana, S. F. Wamba, and R. Dwivedi, “The extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT2): A systematic literature review and theory evaluation,” *Int J Inf Manage*, vol. 57, p. 102269, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.IJINFOMGT.2020.102269.
22. D. A. Sitar-Taut and D. Mican, “Mobile learning acceptance and use in higher education during social distancing circumstances: an expansion and customization of UTAUT2,” *Online Information Review*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 1000–1019, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1108/OIR-01-2021-0017.
23. P. Deng, B. Chen, and L. Wang, “Predicting students’ continued intention to use E-learning platform for college English study: the mediating effect of E-satisfaction and habit,” *Front Psychol*, vol. 14, p. 1182980, Jun. 2023, doi: 10.3389/FPSYG.2023.1182980/BIBTEX.
24. S. S. Chand, B. aklesh Kumar, M. S. Goundar, and A. Narayan, “Extended UTAUT Model for Mobile Learning Adoption Studies,” *International Journal of Mobile and Blended Learning*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1–20, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.4018/IJMBL.312570.
25. A. Strzelecki, “Students’ Acceptance of ChatGPT in Higher Education: An Extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology,” *Innov High Educ*, vol. 49, no. 2, pp. 223–245, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1007/S10755-023-09686-1/TABLES/4.

26. S. Yulianti and R. Widayanti, “Pengukuran Tingkat Kepuasan Pengguna E-Learning Menggunakan Model End User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) di Universitas Esa Unggul,” *IKRA-ITH Teknologi Jurnal Sains dan Teknologi*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 1–10, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.37817/IKRAITH-TEKNOLOGI.V8I3.4160.
27. W. J. Doll and G. Torkzadeh, “The measurement of end-user computing satisfaction,” *MIS Q*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 259–273, 1988, doi: 10.2307/248851.
28. C. Angrayni and E. S. Panjaitan, “Evaluating User Interfaces in E-Learning Satisfaction Using EUCS Method,” *Brilliance: Research of Artificial Intelligence*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 343–354, Jul. 2025, doi: 10.47709/BRILLIANCE.V5I1.6302.
29. A. K. Ameen, I. Y. Maolood, and D. A. Abdullah, “Innovative Approaches to Enhancing User Satisfaction in Higher Education Information Systems,” *Science Journal of University of Zakho*, vol. 12, no. 3, pp. 337–340, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.25271/sjuoz.2024.12.3.1323.
30. M. N. Amin, E. Saputra, M. L. Hamzah, and M. Rahmawita, “Penerapan Metode EUCS terhadap Kepuasan Pengguna Sistem Informasi Akademik,” *Jurnal Teknologi Sistem Informasi dan Aplikasi*, vol. 7, no. 3, pp. 1013–1020, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.32493/JTISI.V7I3.41296.
31. N. A. Hidayah, E. Fetrina, and A. Z. Taufan, “Model Satisfaction Users Measurement of Academic Information System Using End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) Method,” *Applied Information System and Management (AISM)*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 119–123, Oct. 2020, doi: 10.15408/aism.v3i2.14516.
32. A. Padalia and T. Natsir, “End-User Computing Satisfaction (EUCS) Model: Implementation of Learning Management System (LMS) on Students Satisfaction at Universities,” *International Journal of Environment, Engineering and Education*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 100–107, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.55151/ijeedu.v4i3.72.
33. A. Saputri and E. Mulyani, “The Impact of Academic Information System to Students’ Satisfaction in Higher Education,” *Studies in Educational Management*, vol. 12, pp. 1–9, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.32038/SEM.2022.12.01.
34. Niel Agrisman Barus, Iskandar Muda, and Sambas Ade Kesuma, “A Systematic Review of the DeLone & McLean Model in Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems Success,” *Journal of Modern Accounting and Auditing*, vol. 21, no. 3, Jun. 2025, doi: 10.17265/1548-6583/2025.03.002.
35. M. Darriel, A. Aksana, A. Pratama, and S. Mukaromah, “Evaluating ERP System Success Through the DeLone and McLean Model in Financial Organizations,” *bit-Tech*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 243–253, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.32877/BT.V8I1.2513.
36. H. A. Faris *et al.*, “DeLone and McLean Model Analysis of Success Factors of SIDEMANG Application in Palembang City,” *Jurnal Sisfokom (Sistem Informasi dan Komputer)*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 154–161, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.32736/SISFOKOM.V13I2.1894.
37. W. H. DeLone and E. R. McLean, “The DeLone and McLean Model of Information Systems Success: A Ten-Year Update,” *Journal of Management Information Systems*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 9–30, 2003, doi: 10.1080/07421222.2003.11045748.
38. K. Çelik and A. Ayaz, “Validation of the Delone and McLean information systems success model: a study on student information system,” *Educ Inf Technol (Dordr)*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 4709–4727, May 2022, doi:10.1007/S10639-021-10798-4/METRICS.
39. V. Sarasi, I. Chaerudin, and I. A. Sundoro, “The DeLone and McLean model for measuring success in online learning systems: Indonesian evidence,” *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 566–574, Nov. 2023, doi: 10.11591/EDULEARN.V17I4.20839.
40. T. Widyaningrum, Q. Sholihah, and B. S. Haryono, “The Delone and McLean Information System Success Model: Investigating User Satisfaction in Learning Management System,” *Journal of Education Technology*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 86–94, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.23887/JET.V8I1.71080.
41. V. S. Sukandi and M. Ariyanti, “Analysis acceptance and use of CeLOE learning management system (LMS) Telkom University using unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) and Delone-McLean Model,” *Contemporary Research on Management and Business*, pp. 252–255, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1201/9781003295952-64.
42. J. A. Luft, S. Jeong, R. Idsardi, and G. Gardner, “Literature Reviews, Theoretical Frameworks, and Conceptual Frameworks: An Introduction for New Biology Education Researchers,” <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.21-05-0134>, vol. 21, no. 3, p. rm33, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1187/CBE.21-05-0134.
43. M. J. Page *et al.*, “The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews,” *BMJ*, vol. 372, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1136/BMJ.N71.
44. A. Carrera-Rivera, W. Ochoa, F. Larrinaga, and G. Lasa, “How-to conduct a systematic literature review: A quick guide for computer science research,” *MethodsX*, vol. 9, p. 101895, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.MEX.2022.101895.

45. D. Turnbull, R. Chugh, and J. Luck, “Systematic-narrative hybrid literature review: A strategy for integrating a concise methodology into a manuscript,” *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, vol. 7, no. 1, p. 100381, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.1016/J.SSAHO.2022.100381.
46. S. Sarkar and G. Bhatia, “Writing and appraising narrative reviews,” *Journal of Clinical and Scientific Research*, vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 169–172, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.4103/JCSR.JCSR_1_21.